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Lapland Longspur
Long-tailed Duck

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FRONT COVER: Indian Courser from Osman Sagar Lake, Telangana
PHOTOGRAPHER: Sriram Reddy

BACK COVER: Black-winged Kite from Singur, Hooghly, West Bengal
PHOTOGRAPHER: Kallol Mukherjee

Both: Sarabjeet Kaur

189, 190. A male Great Slaty Woodpecker feeding on the seeds of *Mallotus philippensis* (Top) and a female showing a throat with diffused black coloration (Bottom) from the same family group observed prior to the 2019 breeding season in March.

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A Whiskered Tern *Chlidonias hybrida* from Buhchangphai, Mizoram

On 15 June 2022, we visited Buhchangphai (24.33°, 92.67°E; 42 m asl) which is 22 km north from Kolasib town, in northern Mizoram, India. The area is rich in bird life, since there are paddy

fields and fishponds, as well as some forested areas. After observing and photographing birds such as Baya Weaver *Ploceus philippinus*, Bronze-winged Jacana *Metopidius indicus*, Bengal Bushlark *Mirafra assamica*, and Cinnamon Bittern *Ixobrychus cinnamomeus*, we also see three Oriental Pratincoles *Glareola maldivarum* flying high and crossing our path. Soon after, we were surprised to see a lone, unfamiliar light-grey bird with red bill and legs and black crown, that approached us and alighted on power cables besides a few Blue-tailed Bee-eaters *Merops philippinus*, before flying off again in a few minutes. We searched the nearby area to get another look at it, but only saw Watercock *Gallicrex cinerea*, some kingfishers *Alcedinidae* sp., and Scaly-breasted Munia *Lonchura punctulata*. Meanwhile, we consulted the Merlin app on our mobile phones, and arrived at a preliminary identification of the bird as a Whiskered Tern *Chlidonias hybrida*.

The bird was photographed from a distance of c.150 m. It was light grey with black crown and white cheeks and sides of the neck, which give its “whiskered” appearance. The wings extend beyond the tail during rest [191]. The long wings, grey rump, and weakly forked tail are clearly visible in flight [192]. Moreover, the red bill and legs, typically seen in their breeding plumage, were also observed. Identification was confirmed after consulting descriptions and illustrations in Ali & Ripley (1983) and Grimmett *et al.* (2013) as no other tern species of this size has a combination of black cap, grey rump, shallow tail, and red bill.

The Whiskered Tern has a wide range, spreading over Africa, Asia, Europe, and Australia, and is a winter visitor or passage migrant in most of parts of the Indian Subcontinent (Ali & Ripley 1983; Grimmett *et al.* 2013; Gochfeld *et al.* 2020). It is reported to breed in North Cachar in Assam, Kashmir, Delhi,

Thanihana Hauhnar

191. Whiskered Tern showing conspicuous white cheeks, red bill, red legs, and neck contrast with the black crown and light grey body.

Christopher J.Z. Lawlor

192. Whiskered Tern showing grey rump and weakly forked tail.

Uttar Pradesh, and Bihar, as well as in Bangladesh (Ali & Ripley, 1983). Hussain *et al.* (2018) have also reported the presence of breeding Whiskered Terns from Son Beel (24.67°N, 92.45°E) in the adjoining Karimganj District of Assam. Ranade (2021) has reported on nesting colonies of Whiskered Terns in Morigaon, Kamrup, and Sivasagar districts of Assam. Choudhury (2022) has reported it as an uncommon resident or winter visitor in Barak Valley of Assam. Hence, its presence further south in Mizoram is not unexpected.

However, sighting or presence of Whiskered Tern has so far not been mentioned in any of the literature on avifauna of Mizoram, such as Choudhury (2006), Kasambe (2014), and Lalhanzara and Kasambe (2015), nor in citizen science databases like eBird (2023).

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Black-necked Grebe *Podiceps nigricollis* in Jammu and Kashmir

Black-necked Grebe *Podiceps nigricollis* is a small gregarious species having a wide distribution, from Europe through Asia, wintering in the south-western Palearctic, east Asia, and east Africa. It has also been found breeding in southern Africa, south-west Canada, western USA, and central Mexico (Cherkaoui *et al.* 2014, Cullen *et al.* 2020). It is found locally from British Isles to West Siberia, south to Morocco, Iraq, Afghanistan, and east to India and Pakistan (Cullen *et al.* 2020). The nominate subspecies occurs in India. In India, its breeding has been reported from the Union Territory of Ladakh (Gyalpo 2022). It winters in western Gangetic Plains, Gujarat, and central Nepal and is a straggler east to eastern Assam Valley and Bangladesh, south to coastal Orissa and Pune, Maharashtra (Rasmussen & Anderton 2012). Here, we report the sighting of a Black-necked Grebe from the Union Territory of Jammu and Kashmir (J&K), India.

The bird was sighted during a survey along the Hokersar wetland (34.10°N, 74.71°E; c.1,580 m asl), a perennial protected wetland reserve and a Ramsar site c.10 km northwest of Srinagar city in J&K. On 08 March 2022, at 1530 h, we saw one Black-necked Grebe along with Common Coots *Fulica atra*. The bird was in basic plumage and identified based on bright red iris, black top of the head and mantle, neck black on back and grey on front, white breast, rump, and belly [193, 194]. The bird was shy

193. Black-necked Grebe at Hokersar wetland on 08 March 2022.

Haftizullah Sofi

194. Black-necked Grebe at Hokersar wetland on 08 March 2022.

Ansar Ahmad